

closed. The percentage of infested stems and the average number of nematodes per stem (P) were estimated using the procedure described by Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4 [3]:10–11).

In early July, a field with plants showing symptoms of ufra attack (a faint chlorotic splash pattern on the young leaves), sown in early March, was found

at Matlab Bazar in south Comilla.

Samples were taken from this field on alternate weeks (see figure).

The percentage of infested stems first decreased as the water level rose from less than 0.3 m to more than 2.5 m. Some heavily infested stems were submerged, providing a source of nematodes for secondary infestation by waterborne

inoculum. After that, the growth of the percentage of infestation was similar in the tank and in the field. The 3-week lag between the 2 growth curves represents the difference in time of flooding. The growth in average number of nematodes per stem also corresponded closely. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice root weevil in Haryana

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The rice root weevil, formerly a minor pest, has destroyed rice crops in Haryana in the past 3–4 years.

The attack is mainly by *Hydronomolus molitor* Faust (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Another allied species, *Bagous* sp., occurs with it. Its infestation of rice in India may be the first so far recorded. The grubs of the two species are similar in appearance, but the adults can easily be distinguished. *H. molitor* adults are shorter than *Bagous* adults (4.0–4.5 cm vs 4.5–5.0 cm long), and thicker.

These species and the white grub *Holotrichia insularis* Br. are comparable in nature of damage and life cycle. The grubs feed on rice roots from July to mid-September, then rest in the deeper soil layers during later months. They begin to attack within 2 weeks after transplanting in July, completely checking plant growth. Attacked plants do not tiller and remain stunted; their leaves turn yellow. Yield losses in attacked fields amount to 30–50% or more. Normally 1–2 grubs/plant in the initial growth stage will cause economic damage. Incidence is maximum in August. During the hot summer months the grubs are found in earthen cocoons, 14–30 cm deep, in compact soil. The adults emerge in June–July and feed on grasses in the absence of rice, then lay eggs in the rice fields.

Incidence of root weevils^a in Haryana, India.

Grubs (no./plant) in		
1977-78	1978-79	1979-80
14.2	18.1	4.2
13.7	11.3	7.9
18.9	24.7	3.2
17.3	10.7	5.4
15.1	15.8	4.2
14.5	14.8	4.0
13.8	7.1	5.1
21.4	14.2	5.8
17.4	19.4	4.5
14.3	17.5	4.2

^aAv, 9 plants.

The yearly grub incidence in August in fields near the Kaul Rice Research Station averaged 13.7–21.4 grubs/plant in 1977–78; 7.1–24.7 grubs/plant in 1978–79; and 3.2–7.9 grubs/plant in 1979–80 (see table). The lower incidence in 1979–80 may be attributed to drought that season.

The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology identified the insects. ■

Present and future gall midge control strategies in South China

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A change in the cropping patterns of South China to two or three rice crops per year has resulted in outbreaks of gall midge *Orseolia oryzae*. In the past when rice was not available year round, the gall midge overwintered as larvae in the weed *Leersia hexandra* and in wild rice *Oryzae rufipogon*. But gall midge survival on these alternate hosts was low and the gall midge problem was less.

Control strategies based on 5 years of experiments have been implemented over the past 2 years to significantly decrease gall midge damage. These strategies combine cultural control, chemical control, and conservation of natural enemies. The development of host plant resistance and population forecasting with pheromones is being studied.

Cultural control involves timing the rice crops during periods of the year when the relative humidity is unfavorable to the gall midge. A high relative humidity (about 94%) is essential for larvae to hatch and penetrate into the rice tissue. Periodic draining of the fields during periods of favorable relative humidity is practiced. The continuous rice cycle is also broken by crop rotation or the establishment of rice-free fallow periods. The overwintering weed *L. hexandra* is removed by hand from the fields and field borders during the fallow periods.

Chemical control involves spraying or dusting during the peak of adult emergence, the rice tillering stage. The most effective insecticides are pyridofenthion, diazinon, dimethoate mixed with trichlorfon, and pyrimoxythion (N-23) [0-0-diethyl-0 (2-methoxy-4-methyl-pyrimidyl-6, phosphorothionate)]. A seedling dip with 0.1% trichlorfon is generally recommended to conserve natural enemies of the gall midge.

Root-zone application and soil incorporation of granules are popular among rice farmers in Kwangtung, Kiangsu, and other provinces. Root-zone application of pyrimoxythion or carbofuran, either in the seedbed or the field, was effective and is safe to parasites